

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Kontra**FIRST NAME:** Jesse**PROGRAM CODE:** DIPH**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** RP1**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
The author did not use Zotero to insert references
The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord v1629 on MacOS)

ESSENTIAL WRITING CONCEPTS

1) INTRODUCTION

This response paper intends to review some of the essential concepts of academic writing which have been reviewed in the ACA-401D coursepack. As a student who has been away from academia for a number of years, I am finding that many of the concepts and materials that I am now being presented is a refresher to information that I have long since learned. There is a large amount of new learning that I am already experiencing in my first learning period. Approximately half of the materials being presented in this first period is new learning for me. The use of a distance learning platform presents unique learning opportunities and challenges. The course is serving as a great reminder of the importance of language, and words. The ability to study at an international university is a true cultural gift. In order to get the most out of this learning environment I am re-learning the importance of writing, formatting, and referencing so that my work product can be presented and reviewed effectively in a cross cultured community.

2) REVIEW OF THE BASIC ESSAY

The material provided in my first coursepack included a quick reference review of the basics of essay writing (EUCLID 2015, 2). This review was especially helpful to me as it had been a number of years since I had last written an essay. The quick reference was efficient in reminding the reader of the important basic steps of essay writing from conceptualizing your writing, organizing ideas, and building an essay to drafting and editing your final product. The steps were easy to follow and not unnecessarily wordy for a review document. I reflected as I was reading on my writing style. The time and work

that have traditionally been used in the preparation of an essay have been cut short in my writing process. It has been common practice for me to begin the writing process and then continue the conceptualization process as the document is coming together. The conceptualization and structuring of a document is an important part of the process and one that I hope to utilize better in the future to improve my efficiency in written communication.

3) AVOIDING PLAGIARISM

One of the important pitfalls that I have always tried to avoid in my writing is inadvertent plagiarism. Plagiarism does not have to be intentional. In my undergraduate and graduate experience, it has always been illustrated that plagiarism is using another person's words without giving proper credit. I am learning that this is only part of the plagiarism story. Paraphrasing has the ability closely resemble plagiarism if the author does not do it correctly. It is not enough to simply present another person's work in your own words. The language, writing style, and sentence structure must not mimic that of the original author (EUCLID 2015, 14-15).

Plagiarism is such an important concern that it is not enough to not use the exact words of another. Every effort must be made to show that this is your work and not even the writing style or how the information is presented resembles the original author.

4) INTRODUCTION TO AN EXCELLENT PAPER

There is no magic formula for building an excellent paper, but the use of consistent component parts can help the over quality of your work. The coursepack provided a grouping of some important nuggets of information that will help the reader to build a paper that is formatted to present information in a concise production. The coursepack provided important reminders on how to avoid pitfalls that could be encountered without the appropriate preparation such as plagiarism, citation errors, and paraphrasing (EUCLID 2015, 5-16). Even without malintent plagiarism can be encountered and the recommendations were helpful as we begin to build up our writing skills. I found the Lit - 101 review pages within the coursepack to be very helpful in its short and concise recap of important points. I found in reviewing this document that I knew and understood many of the important points that have been highlighted. I was disappointed and somewhat ashamed to admit that although many of these keystones of grammar I do know, my speech has become lazy and I look forward to retraining my brain to a more proper use of language.

The coursepack provided recommendations on improving your academic writing style that already began to put into practice. The recommendation provided that the use of contractions should not be used in more of academically focused publications. I have for many years used contractions without giving much thought as to their what they say about my writing style. I plan to use them progressively as my writing style unlearns the use of contractions in my papers.

5) **BRITISH ENGLISH AND ITS VARIANTS**

In a multicultural environment such as the one created at Euclid University; it is important to remember that what is considered correct in one country may be very different in another. It is with this in mind that students are asked to identify in their writings which style and structure they will be using in. I had never paid any particular attention to the consideration of the origins of American English or the many influences that played a role in its development. It was surprising for me to learn that the population of the United States as well as the magnitude of higher education played a larger part on the dominance of American English (EUCLID 2015, 55-59).

In reviewing the reference materials provided I have found that for many years I have been using a hybrid of American and British English. This blended type of writing is not proper, however, it has provided me with experience and exposure to both variants.

6) **RULES OF THUMB**

There were a number of tips that I consider to be good paper writing hygiene presented in our first coursepack. The main thesis of a paper should be stated early and preferably in the first paragraph (EUCLID 2015, 43). Following the main concepts, the author should spend the bulk of their time focused on the important points or aspects of their chosen topic. There must be a clear effort to support the assertions that you are writing about and your words should be concise and intentional.

I find difficulty at times being wordy. My writing style has typically been one in which I answer the question being asked and move on. In assignments in which there is a minimal word or page requirement, I do find it difficult. I always attempt to use the fewest words in order to accurately and concisely answer the question that is being presented to me. If I attempt to use a word count, or page count, I find myself being unnecessarily verbose in the construction of my arguments. I try to be concise as to not run off topic or distract my reader but admittedly must find balance.

7) **CONCLUSION**

In conclusion, I have found all of the material I have encountered during this first period to be helpful to my learning. The material has presented a blend of new and review materials. Embarking on this new endeavor presents an exciting time for me. This first coursepack has helped to ease some of the trepidation that goes along with any new venture. The number of resources that I have already encountered in this introductory period has helped me to feel supported and has given me additional confidence in my ability to produce quality content.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press. <http://www.eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed August 26, 2019).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.